

Clean Energy Access plan for Secondary Schools focus Kisumu County, Kenya

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Keywords

100% RE	100% Renewable Energy Roadmap
CCG	Climate Compatible Growth
CEP	County Energy Plans
DRE	Decentralized Renewable Energy
DRE	Decentralized Renewable Energy Solutions
EA	Energy Access
EAE	Energy Access Explorer
EAP	Energy Access Potential
EMP-G	Energy Modelling Platform Global
ETIP	Energy Transition and Investment Plan
GHI	Global Horizontal Irradiation
INEP	Integrated National Energy Plan
IEA	International Energy Agency
MCA	Multi-Criteria Analysis
NDC	National Determined Contributions
SEforALL	Sustainable Energy for All

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Executive Summary

The modelling project was done in order to generate locations and technology viability with a focus on electric cooking and solar power in schools. The data used in this was based on vector, raster and tabular formats. The data had to be cleaned, projected and simplified for use in the EAE platform through the QGIS platform.

The approximate number of people living in the area covered by the analysis were **1,217,702** (**population in Kisumu County**) (WorldPop, 2020). Additionally, approximately **640,882** people are living within 1 km of an electricity line. There are also 42 supply points as power sub-stations. As Kisumu county is transitioning towards 100% RE by 2050 focusing on Cooking, Transport

and Electricity, with the electricity services for schools energy needs project to be expanded throughout Kisumu county and nationally.

Main findings of results

1. Electric cooking was a viable solution in schools that were closest to the grid connected distribution transformers. All the 8 schools showed a high energy access potential.
2. *The schools were all connected to the grid and the one furthest to a sub-station was 10km. None of the schools was more than 1 km away from the distribution transformer.*

The Energy Access Explorer platform can be used to develop reports and provide data informed, multicriteria analysis (MCA) based on the attributes of interest to the user. In order to achieve sustainability gains, an accelerator program should be introduced. This will greatly help in improving energy planning with sub-national entities.

Policy advancements can be achieved when decision makers are capacity built to access and provide real-time data for better planning and decision making. Modelling based on reliable data is a good starting point for all the stakeholders involved in making energy decisions for sustainability. In Kenya, the EAE can be used to greatly enhance the county energy plans to inform representative and sustainable National County Energy Plans. The government will need to create partnerships, capacity building, and also allocate budgets for geo-spatial data collection.

1. Introduction

Purpose

To develop an optimum scenario to advance clean energy solutions within schools in Kenya; this will greatly reduce health complications related to unclean cooking and poor lighting thereby improving the experience for students and teachers in schools (Muigua, 2020). Improved health means better results and reduced costs on health issues related to polluting cooking sources hence improved livelihoods around the students.

Scope

This report focuses on 8 secondary schools within Kisumu County. The whole project on data collection covered 100 schools within Kenya. Kisumu county is one of the 47 county governments in Kenya with a 100% renewable energy target by 2050 (Riedemann, 2024). The choice of a deep-dive to Kisumu County geography was to enable in depth insights and capacity building in order to later develop an inclusive county energy plan.

Objective

The research is focused on developing an Energy Access Potential Index (EAP) optimum scenario for electric cooking (clean cooking) and solar development (decentralized renewable energy).

Aim

The aim is to present a model case that can be adopted and used for future energy planning in schools for the extra 80 schools across Kenya covered in the pilot. This strategy can be used to prioritize regions and learning institutions in the future.

Challenge

- i. Linking the energy demand data is selected high schools to the population density in the area. The energy demand is based on the specific schools.
- ii. Identifying Decentralized Energy Solutions based on the available natural resources i.e GHI.

2. Methodology

Modeling Approach/Tool Implemented

The EAE platform was used to model, assess, interact with and present the front end and back end scenarios. The project was done for Kenya and the Kisumu County geography within the Kenya geography. EAE enables an integrated data-driven inclusive energy planning that incorporates the demand and supply parameters in attributes under examination.

Data sources

Data used in this model was primary and desk top research based. Primary data involved short interviews, actual data had been collected and analysed in an excel sheet in December, 2023. The data was collected by a multi-agency stakeholder team working on the energy efficiency programs in Kenya; led by the Ministry of Energy and Petroleum Kenya, SeforALL Kenya and Signify Foundation (Ministry of Energy Kenya, 2019; Ministry of Energy, Kenya (b), 2021). Desktop data came from Kenya National Bureau of Statistics, grid, RWI and global data (solar GHI) among others (World Bank Group, 2021).

Description of EAE scenarios

Scenario	Scenario Description	Key Assumptions
Strategic Energy Planning for Electric Cooking	The schools analyzed are already grid connected and transitioning would spur demand and supply for energy services.	The grid power supply is considered stable when distance is <2 km from distribution transformer
Expansion of Clean Energy Markets (Solar Powered Back-up)	Decentralized Renewable Energy Solutions	The grid is considered unstable when the distance is >2 km from the transformers. Willingness to pay for the solar powered system
BAU	Things stay normal. Energy consumption is not tracked, clean energy solutions are not adopted for cooking and lighting in schools leading negative impacts	Schools are not aware of the impacts of using unclean energy sources. Capacity building is not done to stakeholders both national and from the schools being examined.

Assumptions

Two scenarios are presented with assumptions. In scenario 1 Strategic Energy Planning (Electric Cooking), there is a reliable grid connection indicated by the available transformers around the selected secondary school learning institutions in scenario 1 at <2 km from the distribution transformers. In Scenario 2 (Expansion of Clean Energy Markets - Solar Powered Back-up) that there is unreliable grid connection and stability to warrant use of solar powered back up instead of Gensets. Distance is assumed to be >2 km from the distribution transformers.

It is also assumed that the distribution transformers are indicators of grid energy access to electricity and also power is more stable within the 2 km radius.

3. Results

Main findings of results

3. Electric cooking was a viable solution in schools that were closest to the grid connected distribution transformers. All the 8 schools showed a high energy access potential.
4. The schools were all connected to the grid and the one furthest to a sub-station was 10km. None of the schools was more than 1 km away from the distribution transformer.

Charts and Graphs

Results Scenario 1– Electric Cooking

School Name	Proximity to School Lighting	Sub-station Grid	Distribution Transformers	Sub-County	Co-ordinates	EA potential
Ngere Boys High School	<1km	9km	<1km	Seme	34.45589 -0.12993	High
St. Barnabas	<1km	6km	<1km	Seme	34.50936 -0.12993	High
Dr. Aloo Gumbi	<1km	4km	1km	Kisumu East	34.82931 -0.09312	High
Masogo Mixed	<1km	10km	<1km	Nyando	34.85035 -0.16938	High
Awasi PAG	<1km	12km	<1km	Nyando	35.08527 -0.16938	High
St. Stephen Menara	1km	7km	<1km	Muhoroni	35.23517 -0.17289	High
Thud Dibuoro	<1km	4km	<1km	Nyakach	34.85385 -0.34382	High
Nyabondo	<1km	1km	<1km	Nyakach	34.97745 -0.38063	High

Table 1: Results Scenario 1 – Electric Cooking data extract of the 8 schools based on proximity to grid and Energy Access Potential.

The table 1 above presents a data set focusing on proximity to grid connectivity, location and EA potential per school.

Figure 1: Analysis view of the school lighting project electric cooking top location.

Table 2: Results Scenario 2

Results Scenario 2-GHI

School Name	Proximity to School Lighting	Sub-station Grid	Distribution Transformers	GHI Top 3 Locations	Sub-County	Co-ordinates	EA potential
Dr. Aloo Gumbi	<1km	4km	1km	2279kWh/m2	Kisumu East	34.82931 -0.09312	High
Masogo Mixed	<1km	10km	<1km	2301 kWh/m2	Nyando	34.85035 -0.16938	High
Thud Dibuoro	<1km	4km	<1km	2281 kWh/m2	Nyakach	34.85385 -0.34382	High

Figure 2: Analysis View Energy Access Potential Index Heat map.

Figure 1 above shows the spread of the schools across the county and the related EA potential in both electric cooking and solar development in case the schools will be used as focal points to distribute energy to the community members.

4. Discussion

Insights and results implications

A high EA potential indicates the schools are ideal locations to install electric cooking solutions and also install solar powered back-up systems. Looking at their geo-spatial locations and other related attributes presents an insight into the county connectivity status that is spread across the Kisumu County geography. Table 2 and the EAP map shows the potential for Solar power as DRE choice in the geography even in a MCA scenario where GHI and distribution and transformer layers were jointly assessed and modelled (Global Solar Atlas, 2024). With these insights, adopting either can in future be assessed in terms of capital resource infrastructure needed and adopted on a sustainability scale. Investing electric cooking and solar development will be optimum in the 8 schools on a model based ranking and priority. The roofing in the schools is perfect to hold the panels.

Potential technologies/areas worth exploration/policy recommendations

As a policy measure, schools in the region could be tasked to provide an energy transition plan; the government could then consider this a market place and match the demand and supply potential matrix to finances to accelerate the 100% RE transition. This if replicated across all the counties in Kenya will help improve the environment and also provide financial incentives to the institutions adopting the technology (State Department for Economic Planning, Kenya, 2022). Kisumu County is the model sub-national government in Africa benefiting from the development of 100% RE roadmap to be achieved by 2050 (Pinkard, 2023). Other sub-national governments can then replicate and scale this pilot. Designing the projects would later be done based on the EAE modelling insights.

Limitations of study

The study assumes an optimum scenario where factors considered remain optimum. It does not factor in futuristic changes related to economic, environment, and climate change sensitivities. The report does not look at the RWI but is cognisant of the need to include it in case the same schools can be used as DRE focal points for distribution of power to the surrounding population.

Potential areas for future research

A research on how to include futuristic heat-maps and trends would make the platform key in pre-empting changes to the geographies during the modelling phases.

5. Conclusion

The Energy Access Explorer platform can be used to develop reports and provide data informed, multicriteria analysis (MCA) based on the attributes of interest to the user. In order to achieve sustainability gains, an accelerator program should be introduced. This will greatly help in improving energy planning with sub-national entities.

Policy advancements can be achieved when decision makers are capacity built to access and provide near-real-time data for better planning and decision making. Modelling based on reliable data is a good starting point for all the stakeholders involved in making energy decisions for sustainability. In Kenya, the EAE can be used to greatly enhance the county energy plans to inform representative and sustainable National Energy Plans. The government will need to create partnerships, capacity building, and also allocate budgets for geo-spatial data collection.

Sustainability Plan

Development of a more inclusive and representative energy plan. More stakeholders will be engaged and involved in the consultations process. The insights received from the EMP-G24 will be use to support energy and geo-spatial data planning in Kisumu County. Stakeholder mapping and quarterly meetings within the county are proposed; the various track members within the EMP-G24 could be reconvened to develop local policies and projects.

Future Work

Organization	Sector	Responsibility	Member/s
	Ministries, Private Sector, Public Institutions, Academic & Research Institutions, Development Partners	Serve as the nodal agency in a country for managing EAE. Support the establishment of and lead the EAE Working Group (EAEWG) and convene meetings on a semiregular basis (once per quarter) to share data in a standardized format and ensure the sustainability of the platform	
DW tv, Citizen, Lolwe	Media	Mainstreaming the EAE opportunities to the public to create awareness	Reporters
National Government Institutions (EPRA, REREC, MoEP, KETRACO, GD, KenGen)	National Government and Parastals	Energy Access (EA) report, data on Rural grid extension and densification/ renewable energy (RE) projects, Oversees the sector, policy directives, and data on strategic interventions / future project	Directors
Departments Statistics, M&E, GIS, Planning/Resource, Regulations, Renewable Energy, Operations	County Governments	Source of data for Power generation, transmission & distribution. Data on SPP strategic locations, RE projects with PPA and ongoing, development stage, commissioned, operational, and planned (ALL RE)	M&E focals nd GIS focal points
Maseno Univesrity	Academic & Research Institution	Universities and colleges that conduct training on renewable energy technologies. Universities will be involved in developing the framework and students will have the opportunity of using the collected information.	GIS students
Kenya Association of Manufacturers	Private	Spearheading climate action and energy efficiency within the public sector entities.	Energy Efficiency Experts
SEforALL, IEA, UN, GIZ, ICLEI, UCLG, CoMSSA, AU	Multinationals	Convane regional and national governments to discussing data issues and looking for line budgets	Country Focals
EAE track alumni	Convenor	Support the sustainability conversations and capacity building initiatives.	Trainers and Coaches

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